

INFLUENCE OF CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (CRM), MARKET ORIENTATION, RELATION QUALITY ON MARKETING PERFORMANCE FOR SMEs IN THAILAND

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Abstract

The current study examined the effect of customer relationship management (CRM), market orientation, marketing strategy and relational quality on marketing performance. The indirect effect of relational quality is also examined by the current study. Service small and medium sized enterprises (SEMs) of Thailand are considered in this study to examine the relationship. Therefore, the employees working in SMEs of Thailand are asked to provide response. A questionnaire was used to collect response from these employees. Finally, primary data collected from the employees were analyzed by using statistical tool. Results of the study shows that CRM, market orientation, marketing strategy and relational quality has important contribution to marketing performance. It is found that CRM, market orientation, marketing strategy and relational quality has positive effect on marketing performance. The increase in the activities of CRM, market orientation, marketing strategy and relational quality can promote the marketing performance of SMEs.

Keywords: Customer relationship management (CRM), market orientation, marketing strategy, relational quality, marketing performance.

1. Introduction

Marketing is one of the strategies used by business organizations to promote various products and services (Narayanaswamy & Heiens, 2022). It is one of the important elements of any business industry which has a central role to promote business activities. In any business activity product success in any area is based on the marketing activities of the companies. The successful marketing practices by any business can promote performance of the business and it led towards the survival in competitive business environment. There are different marketing activities adopted by the business organizations to perform better in various products and services. Therefore, marketing performance is most important for businesses. Better level of marketing performance among the companies has the potential to promote products and services. Along with the multinational companies, marketing performance is also important among small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). To promote products and services among SMEs, it is important for companies to promote marketing efforts. The SMEs working in Thailand has vital role to promote any business industry. Therefore, SMEs are the important part of business industry of Thailand (Boonmalert, Ayasanond, Phoothong, & Chaitorn, 2021; That rak, 2021) which required to promote marketing performance. These share of export, import and growth of Thai SMEs is highlighted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Thai SMEs contribution from 2014 to 2018

Source: Office of the SMEs Promotion (2019)

However, these SMEs are facing various problems related to the marketing performance. Despite the significant growth, the marketing performance has not achieved a significant level. All these companies have achieved higher performance as compared to the other businesses; however, the promotion of marketing can further increase the business activity. Although the services of SMEs are quite successful, however, the performance of services can be further promoted by enhancing marketing practices. There are various issues related to the marketing performance such as marketing strategy, skills of the employees, to generate various marketing activities and various other aspects of marketing. Therefore it is needed to promote marketing performance with the help of different activities (E. A. Khan, Royhan, Rahman, Rahman, & Mostafa, 2020).

There are three important elements which can help to shape the marketing strategy among SMEs. The first important element is customer relationship management (CRM) which has central importance to shape the marketing strategy among the service SMEs of Thailand. Better relationship with customers can promote marketing strategy which may lead to the marketing performance. Furthermore, market orientation of the SMEs also has central importance. It is important for SMEs to judge the market and work accordingly and make their strategies to promote services. Therefore, marketing orientation is a second important element which can help to promote marketing. Third most important element is relational quality. The better management of relationship with the stakeholders also promotes marketing performance with the help of marketing strategy. Thus, the current study proposed that CRM (Prasetyo, Wardhana, & Fitriyah, 2022), market orientation and relational quality can promote marketing performance through marketing strategy.

Finally, the objective of the present study is to examine the role of CRM, marketing orientation, marketing strategy and relational quality in marketing performance of SMEs working in Thailand. Number of studies conducted on marketing performance (Gunawan & Sulaeman,

2020; Khamaludin et al., 2022), however, in service SMEs of Thailand the role of CRM, market orientation and relational quality is rarely tested. In addition to marketing activities, it is addressed in SMEs, however, the mediating role of marketing strategies is less focused by previous studies. Therefore, the current study has vital contribution to the literature with the help of introducing unique relationship between variables.

2. Literature Review

Marketing activities can be described as the marketing activities performed by a business to promote the success of the products as well as services. There are several factors influencing marketing performance of any company (Al-Gasawneh, AlZubi, Anuar, Padlee, & Saputra, 2022). In this way, the current study focused on three major factors which may have influence on marketing performance of SMEs. These factors include; CRM, market orientation and relational quality. This study examined the relationship of these three factors in relation to the marketing performance. This study also considered marketing strategy as an influential element for marketing performance. The framework of the current study is shown in Figure 2 which highlighted the relationship between CRM, market orientation, marketing strategy, relational quality and marketing performance.

Figure 2: Framework of the study showing the relationship between CRM, market orientation, marketing strategy, relational quality and marketing performance

2.1 Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

CRM is a procedure in which a business or other organization administers its connections with customers, typically using data analysis to study large amounts of information (Agbemabiese, Hashim, Ho, & Sambasivan, 2022; Del Vecchio, Mele, Siachou, & Schito, 2021; Prasetyo et al., 2022). The management of relationship by the businesses with the customers is an art. This becomes the major source of the company if the company manage the relationship with the

customers effectively. The management of relationship with the customers as well as with the stakeholders has central importance for any business activity. Most importantly it is most significant part of service industry as compared to the manufacturing industry. For the service industry, it is majorly based on the service delivery to the customers in which the relationship with the customers is most important. Similar with other organizations, SMEs also needed to develop good relationship with the customers because it has several advantages in relation to the marketing activities of the company along with the quality of relationship. CRM has significant influence to promote relational quality with the customers. The relational quality is the quality of relationship which promote the satisfaction among the customers. The better management of relationship lead to the higher relational quality with the customers and ultimately it has significant role to boost up the marketing performance. As marketing performance is the vital part of any organization, therefore, it can be promoted with the help of relational quality. Therefore, this study proposes that CRM has positive influence to enhance the quality of the relations among the customers as well as companies (Yadav & Singh, 2018). Furthermore, the promotion of relational quality with the help of CRM has the potential to promote marketing performance. Therefore, following hypotheses are proposed;

Hypothesis 1: CRM has positive effect on relational quality.

Hypothesis 2: CRM has positive effect on marketing performance.

2.2 Market Orientation

The marketing orientation activities by the company is always focused on various needs of customers (Acosta, Crespo, & Agudo, 2018; Boonmalert, Phoothong, Nualkaw, & Klakhaeng, 2020). It majorly focused on the identification of different needs of the customers and produced customized services. It focused on the desire of the consumer that the demand of the customer is important for the company and it is helpful to increase the satisfaction level among the customers. The creation of various products along with those services in line with the needs as well as desires of the customers is most significant part of any business activity. Therefore, market orientation can be described a method to business that prioritizes recognizing the requirements and desires of consumers along with creating products as well as services that satisfy them. It is also one of the most significant parts of any marketing Activity. The promotion of marketing activities to promote services success is majorly based on the market orientation of the company. It is because it helps to fulfill the needs of the customer by producing the customized products (Mourtzis, Zogopoulos, & Xanthi, 2019). In this direction, the current study highlighted that market orientation is another important element of SMEs which can influence the marketing performance. It has direct effect on marketing performance along with the indirect effect of relational quality. Market orientation of the business has effect to produce good relationship (Nurlaely, Sularso, & Panjaitan, 2019) with the customers which help to promote relational quality. The further relational quality improvement has the potential to promote marketing performance. Therefore, this study highlighted that relational quality has influence on marketing performance through market orientation. Hence, it is proposed that;

Hypothesis 3: Market orientation has positive effect on relational quality.

Hypothesis 4: Market orientation positive effect on marketing performance.

2.3 Marketing Strategy

Another important factor which has influence on the relational quality as well as marketing performance is marketing strategy. All the businesses always focus to promote various marketing strategies as a marketing tool which can help to enhance awareness among the customer. Marketing strategies always in line with the customers and it always focuses to promote various services in relation to the customer demands and it focus to produce customized products (Stump, Athaide, & Joshi, 2002). Therefore, marketing strategy is also an important role in relational quality. The marketing strategy of the company is to promote products and services in line with the demand of customers which increase the quality of relationship. The quality of relationship further strengthen the marketing performance (Ardyan & Sugiyarti, 2018; Mohammed & bin Rashid, 2012). Because marketing performance is majorly based on the success of services which is possible with the help of quality relationship with the customers. The previous studies also highlighted that marketing and relational quality has significant vital relationship which has influence on businesses. It is in line with the relational marketing (Salari, Yazdani, & Arab Sorkhi, 2018). Therefore, marketing strategies has positive role to promote relational quality which further lead to the marketing performance. Hence, following hypotheses are proposed;

Hypothesis 5: Marketing strategy has positive effect on relational quality.

Hypothesis 6: Marketing strategy has positive effect on marketing performance.

Hypothesis 7: Relational quality has positive effect on marketing performance.

Hypothesis 8: Relational quality mediates the relationship between CRM and marketing performance.

Hypothesis 9: Relational quality mediates the relationship between market orientation and marketing performance.

Hypothesis 10: Relational quality mediates the relationship between marketing strategy and marketing performance.

3. Method of the Study

3.1 Research Design

Although there are several methods available in the literature to examine the relationship between CRM, market orientation, relational quality, marketing strategy and marketing performance. However, the selection of most important and relevant research method is most important to examine this relationship. The results of the relationship are also based on the selection of appropriate research method. By considering the importance of research method the current study examined the previous studies and it is found that number of previous studies examined these variables with the help of primary data by using quantitative research approach. Therefore, this study used quantitative research in which primary data is used to check the

relationship between these variables. Furthermore, to collect primary data this study used questionnaire survey and cross-sectional research design is used for data collection.

To design a research questionnaire, the current study measured CRM with the help of relationship of the company with the customers of the company. In this measurement the current study considered the policies as well as different activities to build a relationship with customers. Furthermore, market orientation is considered by considering the orientation of the company towards the market. In this way, this study observed the orientation of the company to adopt various changes in the marketing. Additionally, relational quality is measured by the level of quality of relationship by the company with the customers. Furthermore, this study considered marketing strategy by examining the overall strategy of the company towards the marketing activities. Nevertheless, the dependent variable, namely; marketing performance is measured by examining the success of marketing activities of SMEs. The marketing practices adopted by the SMEs are required to achieve a certain level to promote products and services. In this direction, it is observed that whether the marketing activities are promoting the products and services.

After the development of study questionnaire, the current study distributed the questionnaire among the respondents. The questionnaires were distributed among the employees working in service SMEs of Thailand. In this way, 500 questionnaires were distributed by using convenience sampling technique. The convenience sampling is used because it is most suitable in the current study. From total distributed questionnaire's, the current study received 235 questionnaires. From these questionnaires, five questionnaires were not usable because these questionnaires were missing significant part of the questionnaire. Finally, 230 questionnaires were used in data analysis.

4. Data Analysis

Data analysis of this study is started with the help of data screening. As data screening is most important before to examine the relationship between variables. Because it is based on to remove various errors in the data. While data entry in the excel sheet, various errors such as missing value as well as outlier in the data is possible. Both these errors have a tendency to change the original research results. Therefore, to get original results, the current study performed data analysis to fix various errors in the data. Finally, the clean data statistics are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Data Statistic

	No.	Missing	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness
CRM1	1	0	1.911	2	1	5	0.896	1.177	1.083
CRM2	2	0	1.943	2	1	5	1.171	1.266	1.426
CRM3	3	0	1.766	2	1	5	0.805	1.796	1.188
CRM4	4	0	1.69	2	1	5	0.849	2.716	1.522
CRM5	5	0	2.025	2	1	5	1.185	0.939	1.31
MO1	6	0	1.918	2	1	5	1.025	2.064	1.449
MO2	7	0	1.848	2	1	5	1.02	0.854	1.177
MO3	8	0	1.924	2	1	5	0.997	1.624	1.353
MO4	9	0	1.804	2	1	5	0.889	1.411	1.27
RQ1	10	0	2.006	2	1	5	1.076	1.193	1.279
RQ2	11	0	1.842	2	1	5	1.034	1.556	1.431
RQ3	12	0	1.905	2	1	5	1.095	1.77	1.474
RQ4	13	0	1.728	2	1	5	0.925	3.426	1.731
MS1	14	0	1.962	2	1	5	0.993	1.069	1.173
MS2	15	0	2.171	2	1	5	1.121	0.055	0.911
MS3	16	0	1.696	2	1	5	0.847	4.293	1.763
MS4	17	0	1.994	2	1	5	1.111	1.258	1.327
MP1	18	0	1.962	2	1	5	1.049	1.104	1.24
MP2	19	0	1.93	2	1	5	1.032	1.495	1.292
MP3	20	0	2.177	2	1	5	1.22	0.109	1.008
MP4	21	0	2.076	2	1	5	1.167	0.188	1.058
MP5	22	0	2.247	2	1	5	1.231	-0.226	0.896

After data screening, it is ensured that data is suitable to proceed for further analysis to examine the relationship between variables. The current study used partial least square (PLS) which is most important and prominent data analysis instrument which is recommended in several previous studies (Chairatana, 2021; G. F. Khan et al., 2019). In this data analysis technique, the first step is based on to check the reliability along with the validity. Figure 4 shows that

marketing strategy is measured with the help of four items. It is observed that all the scale items have loading above 0.5. CRM is measured with the help of five items with all items having loadings above 0.6. Furthermore, marketing orientation is measured through four items and all the items have loadings above 0.5. The mediating variable namely relational quality is measured with the help of four scale items and all the scale items having factor loading above 0.7. Finally, the dependent variable is measured with the help of marketing performance through five items. It also has factor loading about 0.6. Therefore, internal item reliability is achieved by the current study. All the factor loadings are also shown in Table 2.

Figure 3: Measurement Model

Table 2: Factor Loadings, CR and AVE

Variables	Items	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
CRM	CRM1	0.668	0.781	0.85	0.533
	CRM2	0.783			
	CRM3	0.699			
	CRM4	0.688			
	CRM5	0.802			
Market Orientation	MO1	0.776	0.774	0.854	0.595
	MO2	0.777			
	MO3	0.796			
	MO4	0.735			
Marketing Performance	MP1	0.661	0.795	0.859	0.55
	MP2	0.783			
	MP3	0.762			
	MP4	0.815			
	MP5	0.676			
Marketing Strategy	MS1	0.755	0.701	0.798	0.502
	MS2	0.781			
	MS3	0.748			
	MS4	0.519			
Relational Quality	RQ1	0.775	0.737	0.835	0.559
	RQ2	0.709			
	RQ3	0.757			
	RQ4	0.747			

After the assessment of factor loading the study checked the composite liability (CR) which should be above 0.7. Results of the study shown in Table 2 shows that all the variables namely; CRM, marketing strategy, marketing orientation, relational quality and marketing performance have composite liability above 0.7. Finally, in this type of data analysis average variance expected (AVE) is examined and it should be above 0.5. It is given in Table 2 all the variables have AVE above 0.5 which confirmed the convergent validity. In addition to this, discriminant validity is also important to achieve which is shown in Table 3 with the help of cross loadings.

Table 3: Cross-Loadings

	CRM	Market Orientation	Marketing Performance	Marketing Strategy	Relational Quality
CRM1	0.668	0.282	0.267	0.431	0.42
CRM2	0.783	0.534	0.516	0.577	0.601
CRM3	0.699	0.315	0.336	0.47	0.491
CRM4	0.688	0.428	0.489	0.374	0.346
CRM5	0.802	0.387	0.457	0.492	0.516
MO1	0.551	0.776	0.581	0.589	0.506
MO2	0.302	0.777	0.52	0.471	0.45
MO3	0.54	0.796	0.477	0.563	0.66
MO4	0.236	0.735	0.439	0.524	0.414
MP1	0.46	0.499	0.661	0.586	0.459
MP2	0.496	0.556	0.783	0.469	0.445
MP3	0.343	0.494	0.762	0.431	0.364
MP4	0.483	0.516	0.815	0.469	0.416
MP5	0.309	0.306	0.676	0.36	0.33
MS1	0.424	0.489	0.468	0.755	0.604
MS2	0.523	0.599	0.577	0.781	0.649
MS3	0.515	0.521	0.416	0.748	0.577
MS4	0.37	0.328	0.293	0.519	0.401
RQ1	0.591	0.557	0.492	0.555	0.775
RQ2	0.437	0.512	0.365	0.685	0.709
RQ3	0.448	0.48	0.385	0.571	0.757
RQ4	0.491	0.44	0.401	0.58	0.747

The first step of data analysis in which reliability and validity is confirmed allowed the current study to proceed further analysis in which the hypotheses of the study are tested. In this type of data analysis, direct effect and mediation effect are considered. In this part of data analysis, the current study checked the direct effect of marketing strategy on relational quality and marketing performance. Results shown in Table 4 highlighted that marketing strategy has significant effect on marketing performance and relational quality which supported this hypothesis. Furthermore, the direct effect of CRM is examined in relation to the marketing performance and relational quality. These two hypotheses are also significant because the t-value is above 1.96 along with the positive beta value. But it is examined that marketing orientation has significant effect on relational quality and it also has a significant effect on marketing performance. Therefore, all the direct effects based on marketing strategy, CRM and marketing orientation is significant in relation to the relational quality and marketing performance.

Figure 4: Structural Model

Table 4: Direct Hypotheses Results

	β	M	SD	T Statistics	P Values
CRM -> Marketing Performance	0.246	0.254	0.075	3.263	0.001
CRM -> Relational Quality	0.216	0.224	0.076	2.864	0.004
Market Orientation -> Marketing Performance	0.39	0.393	0.098	3.963	0
Market Orientation -> Relational Quality	0.175	0.18	0.089	1.962	0.05
Marketing Strategy -> Marketing Performance	0.28	0.291	0.111	2.514	0.012
Marketing Strategy -> Relational Quality	0.537	0.528	0.095	5.661	0
Relational Quality -> Marketing Performance	0.095	0.112	0.02	4.71	0

Finally, this study examined the indirect effect of relational quality which is given in Table 5. Three indirect effects are considered in relation to the relational quality. The first and direct effect is considered between marketing strategy and marketing performance. The second indirect effect is considered between CRM and marketing performance. The third indirect effect is considered between market orientation and marketing performance. Results in Table 5 shows that the indirect effect of relation equality between CRM and marketing performance is significant as the t-value is above 1.96. However, the indirect effect of relational quality between marketing strategy and marketing performance is not significant. Additionally, the

indirect effect of relational quality between market orientation and marketing performance is also not significant.

Table 5: In-Direct Hypotheses Results

	β	M	SD	T Statistics	P Values
Market Orientation -> Relational Quality -> Marketing Performance	0.017	0.022	0.025	0.659	0.51
CRM -> Relational Quality -> Marketing Performance	0.021	0.024	0.01	2.05	0.04
Marketing Strategy -> Relational Quality -> Marketing Performance	0.051	0.06	0.06	0.851	0.395

5. Conclusion

It is concluded that; CRM, market orientation, marketing strategy and relational quality has vital importance to promote marketing performance. As reported by the results; CRM, market orientation, marketing strategy and relational quality has positive effect on marketing performance. The increase in the activities of CRM, market orientation, marketing strategy and relational quality can promote the marketing performance of SMEs. It is observed that; relational quality has positive role to transfer the positive effect on CRM on marketing performance. It is recommended to the SMEs to promote various activities which can facilitate marketing performance to promote business performance. For instance, the companies should promote relationship with customers and maintain the quality of relationship. Better relationship with the customers and a certain level of quality based on the unique relationship has better role to gain higher performance. It is also important for the companies to enhance marketing strategy as a good marketing strategy has the important role in services. Quality of relationship with customers, marketing strategy, market orientation and marketing planning to promote marketing performance has important role. Vital contribution to the success of business activities heavily based on marketing. To get success in services it is important for SMEs is to develop a strong relationship with the customers. In this direction, it is not easy for the companies to develop a strong relationship with customer, however, it is quite possible with the help of quality services. Therefore, this study has vital contribution to the literature which lead to the contribution to practices. This study recommended to add various other factors which has effect on the marketing performance by future studies. There are several other factors which have effect on the promotion of marketing performance which are not highlighted by the current study and there are also factors which have affect negatively on marketing performance and not highlighted by the current study. Therefore, it is also needed to address various negative factors affecting marketing performance.

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